

Entrepreneurship Development of Tribal Women through Self-Help Groups (SHGs) for Economic Empowerment in Tripura

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ABSTRACT

The utmost challenge of the present time that the Government of Tripura has to face is the provision of appropriate social security to the scheduled tribes (STs). Though the constitution has given more than 20 articles on the redressed and upliftment of underprivileged with policies on positive discrimination and affirmative action with reference to scheduled tribes (STs) but still the Scheduled Tribes (STs) constitute the weakest section of Tripura, as well as of India's population, from the ecological, economic and educational perspectives. Considering this, the study "Entrepreneurship Development of Tribal Women through Self-Help Groups (SHGs) for Economic Empowerment in Tripura" traces the initiative of developing employment opportunity through entrepreneurship among the tribal women, in rural areas of Tripura. In this study an effort has also been made to inquire about the problems and challenges facing by these rural tribal women in their desire to bring about a change in their lives. The study is based on secondary as well as primary data and has applies various statistical tools in order to analyze, display and discuss the collected data. An attempt has also been made to assess the present potential of tribal women entrepreneurs, for their sustainable livelihood promotion.

Key word: *Entrepreneurship, Development, Livelihood Promotion, Women Entrepreneurs*

Introduction:

Entrepreneurship Development has played very essential role in achieving the goals of inclusive growth and development by self-employment in the industrial sector. In the context of tribal women entrepreneurs, for inclusive growth¹, entrepreneurship development is very much necessary. The effective application of development programmes for tribal entrepreneurs, especially in the post-globalization era, for the purpose of inclusive growth, as STs is one of the marginalized groups² is a vital need. The programmes implemented by the institutional agencies are positively influencing the marginalized groups like scheduled tribes. The entrepreneurship development programmes are converting occupational mobility over generations and promoting self-employment. Self-employment being a good choice of substitute for employment generation is gaining popularity among all sets of unemployed people, where tribal women are no exception. Thus, government and its different financial agencies have to play effective role in providing proper support and training to tribal women entrepreneurs to promote business activities and develop entrepreneurial abilities and skills among them. In other words, for the optimum welfare and mainstreaming of the rural tribal women entrepreneurs, the institutions have to play a dynamic role by implementation of effective inclusive programmes and policies. Beside these, it is also important to promote the work participation by the rural tribal women in order to motivate them to adopt entrepreneurship for their self-employment as well as development.

In the context of Tripura, the work participation rate of Scheduled tribe's women population, where Scheduled tribes refer to the population of tribal communities scheduled in the Constitution of India. The overall female work participation for Scheduled tribe's has increased from 44.4 percent in 2001 to 44.8 percent in 2011(Censes). Whereas the proportion of the main workers in the state has increased from 23.9 percent in 2001 to 36.1 percent in 2011. And also, the proportion of marginal worker in the state has increased 20.9 percent in 2001 to 59.8 percent in 2011. Tribal economy of Tripura is characterized by its relative

¹ Inclusive growth means economic growth that creates employment opportunities and helps in reducing poverty. It means having access to essential services in health and education by the poor. It includes providing equality of opportunity, empowering people through education and skill development.

²The process whereby something or someone is pushed to the edge of a group and accorded lesser importance. This is predominantly a social phenomenon by which a minority or sub-group is excluded, and their needs or desires ignored.

backwardness and thus needs to undergo developmental changes, where development of entrepreneurship among tribal women can be a vital step. . But for the development of entrepreneurship among tribal women the first and foremost need is to identify the present and potential tribal women entrepreneurs and the effective institutional support available to them. Considering this there is a felt need to assess the institutional support system and its effectiveness in the development of rural tribal women entrepreneurs. And thus, empowerment of women emphasizes not merely raising the power of the person but also the quality of life. To the competence and self-rule woman are individual. Empowerment of women has some other size like social, economic, psychological and political aspect. Social empowerment connotes configuration of social capacity, such as fitness, education, liberty and opportunities to realize. Economic empowerment of women implies right to employment, income, possessions. And the payback separately from of gender differences in neighborhood. Psychological empowerment of women signifies confidence structure, gaining of a sense of efficacy and ability of helplessness. Political empowerment implies equal say in the executive process. In the control structure at all the levels as of restricted to worldwide. All these sizes for empowerment are so tangled with one more that over reliance. On one to the abandon of the last are not probable to employment. Though the Government of India and different state Governments have been implementing diverse programme for rural tribal people. Though, the rural scarcity and joblessness still persevere in the country. This problem is flattering severe and sharp. So, the extremely survival of SHGs group is very relevant to make the people of under poverty line. SHGs group allows them to augment their income, get better their model of livelihood and status in civilization. SHGs act as a means for bringing this part of civilization to the main watercourse. Eventually, the nation reaps the compensation of collectivism.

Theoretical aspects of Entrepreneurship Need:

Keeping in mind the various aspect of entrepreneurship for development some of the related theories which are essential for an entrepreneur, as because the motivated entrepreneurs are more productive and creative than those who are unmotivated. Those are:

Israel Kirzner's Theory of Entrepreneurship:

Israel Kirzner (1935) holds spontaneous learning and alertness as two major characteristics of the entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurship is the transforming of spontaneous learning to conscious knowledge, motivated by the prospects of some gain. Kirzner considers the

alertness to recognize opportunity is more vital than innovation in defining entrepreneurship. The entrepreneur either remedied ignorance or corrects errors of the customers.

Kirzner entrepreneurship model holds:

- The entrepreneur subconsciously discovering an opportunity to earn money by buying resources or producing a good, and selling it.
- Entrepreneur financing the venture by borrowing money from a capitalist.
- Entrepreneur using the funds for his entrepreneurial venture.
- Entrepreneur paying back the capitalist, including interest, and retaining the “pure entrepreneurial profit”.

Mc Clelland’s Theory of Achievement Motivation:

Mc Clelland’s Theory of Achievement Motivation holds that people have three motives for accomplishing things: the need for achievement, the need for affiliation, and need for power. Need for achievement and need for power drive entrepreneurship. David McClelland (1917-1988) considers entrepreneurs as people who do things in a better way and make decision in times of uncertainty. The dream to achieve big things over powers monetary or other external incentives. Mc Clelland’s experiment revealed that traditional beliefs do not inhibit an entrepreneur, and that it is possible to internalize the motivation required for achievement orientation through training.

Push Pull Theory:

Gilad and Levine in 1986 proposed two different theories- Push theory and Pull theory. The “push” theory says persons are forced to opt the way of entrepreneur as there is no other way left for them. External factors such as job dissatisfaction/loss, incapable of switching the job, low salary, or inflexible and boring work push a person to take entrepreneurship as a career. On the other hand, the “pull” theory suggests that individuals are attracted towards entrepreneurial activities because of the high independence, prosperity and self-sufficiency attached to it.

Review of Literature:

The entrepreneurship among women will help them in earning money and becoming economically independent. Due to networking women will develop self-confidence, awareness, empowerment, social security etc. A good example pertaining to the factors behind the motivation of women in entering into entrepreneurship is the study by Singh (1993). Singh in her work “Women Entrepreneurs; Their Profile and Motivation”, where she

discuss about the factors imposing on the entrepreneurial appearance of women are not diverse from those affecting men entrepreneurs. And also, the researcher finds that several women are now eager to become entrepreneurs due to various factors. These factors can be classified under two categories, they are, 'pull factors' and 'push factors. Under the pull factors, the women entrepreneurs choose a career as a challenge and adventure with an urge to do something new and to have an independent occupation. The push factors force women to take up business enterprises to get over financial difficulties due to family circumstances. (Singh, 1993). Again Ray & Biswas (2014) in their working paper "Empowerment of Rural Women through Livelihood Opportunities in Incense (Agarbatti) Sector in Tripura, India" also opines that a number of factors promote the joining of women in the entrepreneurial sector. The study discusses about the overall percentage of women workers in various sectors like 96 percent of women's work in unorganized sector, whereas only 4 percent of women's work in organized sector. Though tribal women of Tripura have substantial contribution as labour but their role is often underestimated and not counted as economic activity. . Though there are a number of encouraging and incremental factors behind the promotion of entrepreneurship among rural tribal women but it is not free from challenges. Several studies has found supporting results, one of such studies is the one by Mohapatra & Rabindra (2012). Mohapatra & Rabindra in their study on "Constraints faced by Tribal Entrepreneurs in Dairy Farming Enterprise" explains that Dairy farming is one of the important enterprises which regulate the financial activities of the tribal people in the rural areas of Odisha in India. Increasing demand for milk and milk products in recent years strengthens dairy farming as money-making enterprise for tribal. The tribal entrepreneurs have been challenging to several limitations in this sector which delay their way for development. This study was undertaken in Mayurbhanj district of Odisha in India, to find out the problems faced by tribal entrepreneurs and to advise appropriate measures to overwhelm these problems. The results discovered that the major problems faced by tribal dairy entrepreneurs were high cost of concentrate (96.67 percent), lack of availability of veterinary literature in the village (79.67 percent) etc. Also, Devi (2014) in her study "Problems and Prospects of Women Entrepreneurship in India" supports the fact that the women in the entrepreneurial sector have to face a large number of challenges. In her study she observed that in modern competitive world the male gendered are getting more importance whereas women are undeveloped for many decades. And the women who want start up their enterprise faces various hurdles. She also describes the various problems they face like gender inequality, problem of investment, absence of education, lack of training and support etc. She also mentions that the government

and the financial institution also should take proper steps to encourage the women entrepreneurs and should make the proper podium to solve their problems..Another study by Deb (2015) entitled “Micro-Entrepreneurship for Women Self-Reliance: A Study in Tripura” also displays various prospect and challenges of women entrepreneurs. In his study he has observed the socio-economic status of women entrepreneurs and factors of involvement in micro entrepreneurship and problem faced by them..

Objectives:

1. To assess the pattern of income and expenditure of the respondents before and after joining SHGs.
2. To give suggestive measures in order to make improvement in the current picture.

Research Methodology:

The research methodology has been outlined in accordance to the objectives under study. The proposed study is based on, the composition of both secondary and primary data. The methodology adopted having both descriptive and analytical where both quantitative and qualitative data has taken in account. For in-depth analysis, along with Survey method, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) has also adopted keeping in view the qualitative nature of this study. Focus group discussions has been held among the tribal single entrepreneurs and the tribal groups of entrepreneurs. This study is based on field survey and interview method with the tribal women entrepreneurs. For the purpose of study, the following 101 samples are collected from west district. The primary data has been collected through a well-designed and structured questionnaire. The structured questionnaire schedule has prepared to understand the actual compliance status of different tribal women entrepreneurs.

Sample Design:

Figure:1

Results & Discussion:

Age	No. of women	Percentage (%)
18-24	4	3.96%
25-31	24	23.76%
32-38	40	39.60%
39-45	16	15.84%
46-52	10	9.90%
53-60	7	6.93%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The table describe that out of 101 respondents the greatest number of tribal women are in the age group of 32 to 38 year i.e. 39.60 percent. It was observed that, this age group members are playing very important role for each group, as because most of them are group leader, president, cashier and secretary. The second highest is 25 to 31 year of age and constitute 23.76 percent of total population. And the third highest is 39 to 45 year of age groups. So, it was clear in the study that this groups of tribal women are actively participating in their works, and the rest others are followed.

Religions	No. of women	Percentage (%)
Hindu	50	49.50%
Christian	51	50.50%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The above table shows the religion status of tribal women SHGs members, where it was founded that the highest percentage of the tribal women are Christian and they said that they have changed the religion status after marriage. And 49.50 percent of the tribal women are Hindu in the study area.

Category	No. of women	Percentage (%)
APL	19	18.81%
BPL	54	53.46%
ADHOC BPL	26	25.74%
ANTODAYA	2	1.98%
Annapurna	0	0%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The table depicts the economic categories of tribal women SHGs members, where it was observed that 53.46 percent of SHGs members are BPL holder. And only 18.81 percent of tribal women are in the category of APL. But 1,98 percent of the members are ANTODAYA and none of the respondents belong to Annapurna category.

Education status	No. of women	Percentage (%)
1-5	41	40.59%
6-8	23	22.77%
9-10	19	18.81%
11-12	12	12.87%
BA	4	3.96%
MA	1	0.99%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

It was observed that, the education status of the tribal women SHGs members are not up to the mark at all, very less percentage of tribal women have avail for higher studies i.e. Bachelor of Arts and Masters of Arts. The highest percentage of education among them is class 6-8. They said that, they have faced various problems like financial, social, lack of transportation, infrastructure etc. for that reasons they can not upgrade their education to higher level.

Marital status	No. of women	Percentage (%)
Married	98	97.02%
Widow	2	1.98%
Divorce	1	0.99%
Separated	0	0%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

This table show the marital status of tribal SHG members. Where, 97.02 percent of the respondents are married. 1.98 percent of the respondents are founded as widow and very less percentage i.e. 0.99 are divorce but none are founded as separate.

Type of family	No. of women	Percentage (%)
Nuclear	83	82.17%
Join	18	17.82%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The above table depicts the type of family of the respondents and it was clear that 82.17 percent of the respondents are staying in nuclear family. Only 17.82 percent of the respondents are staying in joint family.

Do before joining	No. Of women	Percentage
Workers in agriculture field	32	31.68%
Animal husbandry	28	27.72%
Daily labour	21	20.79%
Handloom unit	13	12.87%
Other	7	6.93%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The table describe the occupation of the respondents before joining the SHGs as a profession. And it was founded that, they used to work in agriculture field as agriculture laborers i.e. 31.68 percent. Secondly 27.72 percent of the respondents used to rear pig, poultry etc. and sell their products in the markets once or twice in a year. 20.79 percent of the respondents were daily laborers. Basically, they used to do work in others place. 12.87 percent said, that they used to prepare their traditional cloths i.e. pachar, gamcha etc. but the value for their products was not up to the mark in the market as there was no proper marketing facilities for them. And 6.93 percent used to do some other activities like traditional cooking, part time job in health care center etc. but most of the time there was no earning facility for them in a year.

Table: 8 Age and Income of the respondents before joining SHGs

Income (Rs.)	1000-5000		6000-10000		11000-15000		16000-20000	
	No of women	Percent						
18-24	3	2.97%	1	0.99%	0	0	0	0
25-31	19	18.81%	5	4.95%	0	0	0	0
32-38	27	26.73%	13	12.87%	0	0	0	0
39-45	6	5.94%	0	0	6	5.94%	2	1.98%
46-52	5	4.95%	4	3.96%	1	0.99%	0	0
53-60	5	4.95%	3	2.97%	0	0	0	0

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The above table shows the age groups and income of the respondents before joining SHG. It was founded that in age group of 18-24, 2.97 percent of the respondents use to in between Rs. 1000-5000. Where 0.99 percent tribal women use to earn in between Rs. 6000-10000. 18.81 percent of the respondents in the age of 25-31, use to earn in between Rs. 1000-5000 and 4.95 percent in the group of Rs. 6000-10000. 26.73 percent in the age group of 32-38 and 12.87 percent in the income group of Rs. 6000-10000. But it was also observed that in the age group of 39-45, 5.94, 5.94 and 1.98 percent of the respondents are earning in the income group of Rs. 1000-5000, Rs.11000-15000 and Rs. 16000-20000. And respectively others are followed. It was clear from the picture that, the income of the respondents is not good at all.

Table: 9 Age and Income of the respondents after joining SHGs

Income (Rs.)	After join income 1000-5000		After join income 6000-10000		After join income 11000-15000		After join income 16000-20000	
	No of woman	percent	No of woman	percent	No of woman	percent	No of woman	percent
18-24	2	1.98%	0	0	2	1.98%	0	0
25-31	4	3.96%	13	12.87%	6	5.94%	1	0.99%
32-38	10	9.90%	15	14.85%	15	14.85%	0	0
39-45	2	1.98%	6	5.94%	6	5.94%	2	1.98%
46-52	1	0.99%	3	2.97%	4	3.96%	2	1.98%
53-60	1	0.99%	3	2.97%	3	2.97%	0	0

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The above table described the age groups and income of the respondents after joining SHGs. Where it was seen that, the age group of 39-45 of tribal woman are very active in their work and after joining the SHGs their income increases a lot, where as it was also observed the same, in the age group of 46-52 and 53-60. Most of the tribal women are earning per month in the income group of Rs. 16000-2000, which is a good sign for them, to live a better livelihood. And it was also observed that the income level of the respondents in every age group has increased a lot from earlier.

Before	After	No. of women		Percentage	
		Before	After	Before	After
3000-5000		46	10	45.54%	9.90%
5100-7000		27	32	26.73%	31.68%
7100-9000		21	27	21%	26.73%
9100-11000		7	12	6.93%	11.88%
11100-13000		0	12	0.00%	11.88%
13100-15000		0	8	0.00%	7.92%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The table depicts the expenditure pattern of the respondents. And it shows a positive side and also the increasing pattern of expenditure after starting their business. Firstly, 7.92 percent of the respondents said their expenditure on various head like supporting family, child education, medical facilities and etc. has increased a lot i.e. in between Rs.13100-15000. And now a days they are living a better life from earlier. 11.88 percent of the respondents are coming in the group of Rs. 11100-13000, where as in earlier there are no respondents in this expenditure group. 11.88 percent has increase from 6.93 percent in the group of Rs. 9100-1100. And from 21 percent has increased to 26.73 percent in the group of Rs.7100-9000. So it was a positive vibes for the respondents, as the income level increases the expenditure of the respondents also increased.

Table: 11 Savings Patterns of the respondents				
	Before		After	
Before	No of woman	Percentage	No of women	Percentage
After				
0-500	1	0.99%	9	8.91%
600-1000	6	5.94%	15	14.85%
1100-1500	11	10.89%	33	32.67%
1600-2000	3	2.97%	12	11.88%
2100-2500	1	0.99%	2	1.98%
2600-3000	1	0.99%	2	1.98%
3100-3500	1	0.99%	1	0.99%
3600-4000	0	0	1	0.99%
4100-4500	0	0	1	0.99%
4600-5000	0	0	1	0.99%

Source: Filed Survey, 2019

The table described the status of saving habit among the respondents before and after joining SHGs. And it was seen that, the saving habit of the respondents has increased a lot from earlier. The highest saving habit of the respondents, is in the group of Rs. 3100-3500 i.e. also only 0.99 percent and no one is founded in the group of Rs. 4600-5000 in earlier. But after joining the SHGs their saving habit increased a lot. It was founded that every respondent has the tendency of saving now a days. They also said that, they are saving their earning in various bank, insurance companies and in post office.

Conclusion

Thus, it shows that SHGs play major role for woman empowerment, its changes the living condition of rural poor woman. After joining SHGs women develop their skills, knowledge, and economic conditions, most numbers of woman SHG members start many incomes generated activity because SHGs provide financial support with less interest. In rural areas most of the women is participating SHG and they are very active in their work. Many Government schemes has been set up for the purpose to bring up some changes in the lives of the tribal entrepreneurs, as women is the one who leads the family through all kind of hectic problems that are facing in everyday lives. So, SHGs has given them a chance to be self-entrepreneurs and earn its own money for the purpose to survive as well as for the purpose of

supporting the family. These jobs are taken up as the secondary source of income to start its own business as well as to manage the family and also to provide to their special needs.

Recommendation

1. They should be given proper guidance's and benefits for the purpose to bring the interest in the cooperate society.
2. Many other Schemes like NABARD, and other institutional loan giver should be more prominent to the primary co-operations for encouraging and providing the working capital in time.
3. Government should also encourage them by providing less interest rate loans in order to start their businesses as the entrepreneurship in various fields.
4. Government also should give more chances to those tribal women entrepreneurs to make them participate in all kinds of trade fair to show the works and the handmade designs.

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